

Experimental set-up and protocol to assess eye-hand coordination in telemanipulation¹

Manuela Uliano, Silvia Fattorini, Marco Controzzi
The BioRobotics Institute and Department of Excellence in Robotics and AI
Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, Italy

manuela.uliano@santannapisa.it, silvia.fattorini@santannapisa.it, marco.controzzi@santannapisa.it

Abstract — Gaze and eye-hand coordination play a key role in human manipulation. It's known that eye movements are related to the unfolding task and play an anticipatory role, leading actions by an average time of about 500ms. Due to this predictive nature, the gaze has been extensively investigated for predicting human intention. Toward the goal of implementing a shared autonomy system for telemanipulation, we are investigating gaze and eye-hand coordination in telemanipulation tasks and how they differ from natural manipulation. To this end, we adapted the experimental set-up and protocol published by Johansson R. S. et al. in the study "Eye-hand coordination in object manipulation", which represents a capstone in human behavioural studies. This abstract presents the experimental set-up and protocol.

Keywords— teleoperation; eye-hand coordination; object manipulation; saccadic eye movements.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teleoperation enables humans to remotely control robots, giving them the possibility to operate in hazardous or inaccessible environments, as well as providing support for executing highly precise and repetitive tasks [1]. Consequently, teleoperation finds extensive application in various fields including surgery, assistance, space exploration, and underwater exploration. Nevertheless, the differences in proprioception, visual and haptic feedback, as well as the varying number of controllable degrees of freedom in arms and hands, contribute to the complexity and challenge of teleoperating a robot. Sharing the control of a robotic system with an autonomous controller enables human operators to decrease their cognitive and physical workload during the execution of a remote task and to increase their performances in complex and precise tasks. This led to the development of shared autonomy approaches, where robots can seamlessly adapt their autonomy level based on the understanding of human intentions and the surrounding environment [2]. Anticipating human intentions relies on the robot's ability to perceive human behaviour, achieved through the extraction of different biological signals [3]. The study of gaze behaviour during manipulation tasks has received extensive attention over the years. In natural manipulation tasks, eye movements exhibit a strong correlation with motor actions, prioritizing objects relevant to the task over their appearance [4], [5]. Additionally, eye movements play an anticipatory role, preceding manipulative actions by an average time of approximately 500ms [5]. Research indicates that hands or moving objects are seldom fixated upon [4], [5], while eye fixations are drawn to future contact points of objects, particularly focusing on the anticipated location of the index finger [6], [7]. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that gaze patterns tend to become more erratic with increasing task complexity [8]. All together,

these characteristics make gaze a potentially meaningful signal for decoding human intent. However, telemanipulation tasks are highly different from natural manipulation tasks due to variations in proprioception, visual, and haptic feedback, significantly impacting gaze behaviour and eye-hand coordination. In teleoperation scenarios, several studies have revealed an increase in visual cues towards moving objects and the robot end-effector to compensate for sensory deficits [9]-[11]. Furthermore, irregular occurrences of anticipatory glances towards the object of interest have been noted [12]. Nevertheless, intuitive control of the teleoperation platform facilitates rapid familiarization, resulting in anticipatory glances resembling those observed in natural environments, with reduced reliance on visual checks due to gained expertise [12]. What arises from different studies is the dependency of the gaze on the characteristics of the robot and set-up. Despite the existing literature presenting different studies on gaze behaviour in teleoperation scenarios, to the best of the authors' knowledge, it remains fragmented and lacks clear evidence of principles that could be exploited for intention prediction purposes. Towards the goal of implementing an intention prediction module for shared autonomy in telemanipulation, the present work aims to present an experimental set-up and protocol to investigate how gaze and eye-hand coordination behave in teleoperation scenarios. To this end, we adapted the protocol and the set-up designed by Johansson R. S. et al. in [4], which represents a capstone in human behavioural studies.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The proposed experimental set-up accurately reproduces the one realized by Johansson *et al.* in [4], with the addition of the teleoperation platform. It consists of several components: the teleoperation platform, the participant area, the manipulation environment, and the tracking system.

The *teleoperation platform* comprises the leader and the follower systems. The leader system comprises a wearable motion capture device (Perception Neuron, model PN 32 V2) and a head-worn virtual reality viewer (Varjo, model Aero). The Perception Neuron suit allows tracking the motion of the participant's arm and hand to directly control the motion of the robotic arm and hand, while the Varjo viewer allows projecting the scene looked by the robot to the participant and tracking the gaze. The follower system consists of a 6-axis industrial robotic arm (Universal Robots, model UR5) and an anthropomorphic robotic hand (Prensilia Co. Ltd, model Mia) as its end-effector. In addition, an RGB-D camera (Intel RealSense, model D435i) is positioned on a tripod and adjusted to mimic the typical distance between a human's eyes and hands during object manipulation. The *participant*

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area comprises a chair, a hand support, and a cervical collar. Every experimental trial starts and ends with the participant's hand lying on the hand support, which corresponds to a specific pose of the robot, outside the field of view of the RealSense camera. In addition, the hand support triggers the start and end of the trial by means of a Force-Sensing Resistor (FSR) which detects the contact of the hand with the support (Ohmite, model FSR01CE), while the cervical collar is used to assist the participant in keeping his head still. The *manipulation environment* includes a manipulation bar, a stand, a target area and two types of obstacles of different shapes, rectangular and triangular. The grey manipulation bar is located horizontally on a pre-cut foam, which plays the role of a table and prevents damage to the robotic hand in case of collisions. Eight micro-switches (Omron, model SS-01GL13-E), housed in the pre-cut foam, detect the time of lifting and releasing of the bar. To the left of the bar, the stand is fixed to an aluminium breadboard through a designed housing placed on the table, under the pre-cut foam. The target area is located at the top of the stand and it consists of a housing containing a button that is triggered when the participant correctly touches it with the manipulated bar. Two obstacles with different shapes were employed, rectangular and triangular obstacles. The obstacles adhere to the stand thanks to two small magnets, making it easy to change them. The stand, the target area and the two obstacles are coloured red. Finally, a *tracking system* (OptiTrack, 4xFlex 3 cameras) was employed to obtain the real-time pose of the objects involved in the experiment.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL

The experimental protocol reproduces the methodology outlined in [4], intending to enable direct comparison of the results. Participants are asked, while seated and keeping their head still, to pick the manipulation bar from the table with the index and the thumb fingers, reach the target area with the left end of the bar and bring it back to the table. The task is deemed finished when participants repositioned their hand on the hand support. Since the scene displayed within the viewer is 2D and depth cannot be perceived, we constrained the robot's translation in depth, according to the location of the manipulated bar. We considered 3 experimental conditions, differentiated by the presence and shape of an obstacle: no obstacle (NO), rectangular obstacle (RO), and triangular obstacle (TO). Participants first completed the task under the NO condition, followed by a randomized sequence of the RO and TO conditions. In each condition, the task was repeated 4 times. Before the beginning of the experiment, the required calibrations and the familiarization phase take place. At the beginning of the experiment the participant is seated with his right hand on the hand support, the robotic hand is stationary in the home pose, and a black screen with a fixation dot is displayed within the viewer. Each trial is initiated by an auditory cue, followed by the disappearance of the black screen, allowing the vision, through the viewer, of the manipulation environment. This is the trigger for the participant to begin the task. An additional auditory cue signals the contact with the target area, which occurs when the button mounted on the target is fully pressed with the manipulation bar. After this contact, the participant places back the bar on the table and puts his right hand back on the hand support. The task is then considered completed and the

black screen with the fixation dot is shown again to the participant, while the robotic system automatically returns to its home pose. The experiment aims to identify the attractive landmarks for the gaze, within the trial, across trials and across the different experimental conditions. In addition, the study aims to analyse the spatiotemporal coordination of gaze and hand movements. To address this, time measurements are taken through different sensors. The Force-Sensing Resistor (FSR) under the hand support measures the instant when the participant begins and ends the execution of the task. The eight micro-switches, placed on the pre-cut foam, track the time of lifting and releasing of the bar, while the red button detects the instant when the participant reaches the target with the manipulation bar. The onset time of each trial, marked by the disappearance of the black screen and fixation dot within the viewer, is triggered and saved by the experimenter pressing the 'S' key of the keyboard. Conversely, the termination time is initiated by the activation of the FSR, signalling the placement of the participant's hand on the support and prompting the appearance of the black screen with the fixation dot. In addition, the pose of each object involved in the experiment is recorded. Finally, gaze position data provided by the viewer are recorded, together with the frames streamed by the RealSense camera.

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